

leaffolder except that there was no webbing and tying of leaf margins.

In certain pockets, the young crop was attacked, resulting in stunting and severe drying symptoms. Incidence was higher in shaded areas.

The adult beetle is dark bluish-green, shiny and metallic, elongated with fine striations or pittings on the elytra. The beetles are very weak flyers

and soft, without hardness. The larva is a soft-bodied, campodeiform grub, pale white with a brown head, and with a sclerotized tubular process at the abdominal tip. The larvae arrange themselves in a longitudinal line on the leaf surface, with about 7/leaf on average (maximum 10-12). Fecal pellets found on the surface of affected leaves are very tiny and powdery.

A larva pupates by attaching itself to the leaf surface by its posterior end. About three pale brown pupae could be seen on each leaf. A large number of white pupal skin are seen on leaf surfaces after beetle emergence.

The simultaneous presence of all stages of the pest indicates overlapping broods. □

New sources of resistance to rice leaffolder (LF)

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We screened 1,430 F₄ progenies of TKM6, Muthumanikam, and Ptb 33 crossed to IR4707-106-3-2 during 1988

Reaction pattern of parents and progenies to LF damage, Laurel, Batangas, Philippines, 1988 wet season. Each pattern indicates reaction at sequential 7-d scoring intervals. R = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

wet season in Balakilong, Laurel, Batangas. The progenies had been found resistant in the F₂ and F₃ in greenhouse screening.

Seedlings raised in wet seedbeds were transplanted 21 d after seeding in 2 rows of 25 hills each. Parents and susceptible check IR36 were planted every 100 rows. At 50 d after transplanting (DT), 120 kg N/ha was applied to increase plant lushness that would attract LF adults from adjacent fields.

Plants were scored for plant damage when susceptible check IR36 had more than 50% leaf damage; scoring was repeated every 7 d to harvest.

Damage could not be scored beyond 86 DT, when early-maturing TKM6

progenies had to be harvested. Late-maturing Muthumanikam progenies and Ptb 33 were damaged by a typhoon after the third scoring.

All parents showed resistance to LF at 72 DT. Muthumanikam and Ptb 33 showed intermediate resistance to susceptibility at later stages, almost comparable to the female parent IR4707-106-3-2 and susceptible check IR36 (Fig. 1a). TKM6 progenies had the best resistance (Fig. 1b). Ptb 33 progenies had limited resistance (Fig. 1c). Progenies of both Ptb 33 and Muthumanikam were late-maturing and tended to show intermediate to susceptible reaction to LF at booting. □

Pest resistance—other pests

Analysis of isozymes in rice varieties tolerant of and susceptible to herbicide butachlor

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We examined the relationships of peroxidase and esterase isozymes in indica rice varieties with tolerance for butachlor, to establish a biochemical means of screening for tolerance.

Resistant Wu-Jie-Gu and Long-Jiang-Dao; susceptible Yuan-Feng-Zao, B3, and IR24; and medium-resistant Lu-Hong-Zao 1 were used. Germinated seeds were sown in 5 cm soil in 45- × 25- × 15-cm plastic boxes.

At the 2-3 leaf stage, seedlings were soaked with 100 ppm butachlor solution or water.

At 1-5 d after treatment, electrophoresis was made with 7% polyacrylamide gel system. Peroxidase isozymes were stained with acetate-benzidine and esterase isozymes with 1-naphthyl acetate and fast blue RR salt.

Eleven peroxidase isozymes were separated by electrophoregram (Fig. 1). The tenth isozyme (Rf=0.88) was more active in susceptible varieties than in tolerant or medium varieties treated with butachlor, especially 3 d after treatment. In control, there was no difference between zymograms of tolerant and susceptible varieties.

Six esterase isozymes were identified (Fig. 2). The third isozyme (Rf=0.79)

1. Zymogram patterns of peroxidase isozymes at 2-3 leaf stage (treated with butachlor). 1 = Yuan-Feng-Zao (S), 2 = Wu-Jie-Gu (R), 3 = Lu-Hong-Zao 1 (M), 4 = B3 (S), 5 = Long-Jiang-Dao (R), 6 = IR24 (S).

2. Zymogram patterns of esterase isozymes at 2-3 leaf stage (treated with butachlor). 1 = Yuan-Feng-Zao, 2 = Wu-Jie-Gu, 3 = Lu-Hong-Zao 1, 4 = B3, 5 = Long-Jiang-Dao, 6 = IR24.

existed only in susceptible varieties treated with butachlor; zymograms of samples from control and tolerant or medium varieties lacked the isozyme.

The fifth peroxidase isozyme and third esterase isozyme of B3 were slightly different in position from those of other varieties (Fig. 1, 2).

These results indicate that the tenth peroxidase and the third esterase isozyme of the three susceptible varieties are related to susceptibility. □

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Stress tolerance—drought

Influence of water potential on germination of direct seeded rice

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Germination of direct seeded rice is affected by soil moisture. We studied germination in local varieties Dharial and Katakara and improved varieties BR20 and BR21 in response to water potential.

Six levels of water potential (0, -176, -363, -514, -704, and -837 kPa) were created with 0, 0.5, 0.10, 0.15, 0.20, and 0.25% NaCl solutions. Ten-ml aliquots of solution were added to 9.0-cm petri dishes containing Toyo 44 filter paper. Fifty seed/variety were placed on the

soaked filter paper and the covered dishes were kept on a laboratory bench at room temperature for 9 d. Germination percentages were recorded daily from day 4. Germination was virtually completed by day 8.

Germination of all four varieties was affected by water potential (see table). Maximum germination was at -176 kPa for all four varieties.

However, there was a significant variety x stress interaction. No significant differences in germination were observed from 0 to -514 kPa for Katakara and BR21. BR20 showed 75% germination at -704 kPa. At -837 kPa, Dharial failed to germinate.

Although using NaCl to impose water potential could also have caused salinity stress, it appears that BR20 has good tolerance for drought during germination. □

Germination of 4 rice varieties in response to water potential. BRRI, Bangladesh.

Water potential (kPa)	Germination ^a (%)				
	Dharial	Katakara	BR20	BR21	Mean
0	81 a	87 a	88 a	93 a	87
-176	83 a	90 a	91 a	93 a	89
-363	67 ab	84 a	91 a	89 a	83
-514	63 b	85 a	89 a	85 ab	81
-704	27 c	61 b	75 a	61 b	56
-837	03 d	37 c	27 b	14 c	20
Mean	54	74	77	73	

^aAv of 3 replications. Mean separation in a column by DMRT at the 5% level. LSD (0.05) for comparing variety means in row is 12%.

Stress tolerance-adverse temperature

Effect of synthetic phytohormone analog on leaf water potential during chilling

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We investigated the effect of a new synthetic analog of the phytohormone

abscisic acid (ABA), coded LAB173711 (BASF, FRG), on the water status of rice plants during chilling.

Low temperature-sensitive rice IR36 was sprayed at 36-d-old with 10⁻⁴ mol LAB173711/liter alone or a combination of LAB173711 with growth-retardant tetcyclacis. At 24 h after treatment, the seedlings were transferred to a water tank in the greenhouse and kept at a room temperature of 11 °C for 4 d. Leaf water potential